

NOVASOIL

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QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been circulated among the broader NovaSoil consortium, including their key stakeholders, to ensure the delivery provides up-to-date information, contains no mistakes, and aligns with the multidisciplinary views of all who participated in the NovaSoil project. The following table shows the reviews conducted during the validation process.

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V0.1	13.09.2025	UNIPI, UNIFE	A presentation of the code's structure and included information
2	V0.2	22.10.2025	All	The final draft of code was presented to the wider consortium
3	V.3	24.10.2025	All	The draft was circulated among the consortium partners and the sister project for feedback and more information.

Project Consortium

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1 Summary

The ambition of this code is to provide ethical guidance in soil management governance. At the heart of its focus lies an ethical business model for soil health.

Using case studies from across Europe, this research explored various dimensions of soil-health-oriented land management to determine which practices will benefit soil, ecosystems, landscapes, and human actors across the entire land management chain.

The process of creating this code began with reviewing the existing ethical frameworks (e.g., codes of conduct and ethics) present in prominent European and international soil management-related policies. The aim was to map the ethics-related landscape within existing policies and incentives, and to explore guiding ethical principles for navigating contemporary healthy-soil-oriented land management practices. However, the ultimate goal of this document was to provide guidelines for a corporate governance strategy for healthy soil management that would also align with the daily realities of various stakeholders across soil management businesses (e.g., agriculture, forestry, etc.).

Therefore, it has also been grounded in a co-creative, participatory approach that focused on mapping the ethical values, principles, and considerations of all enrolled stakeholder groups across a couple of dozen workshops, focus groups, and multiplier events.

This code does not provide any definite legal binding steps. Instead, it aims to guide the reader through a rich portfolio of various ethical considerations linked to sustainable soil management. Its goal is to underline that soil health, especially conceived through various business operations, is a process rather than a variable, extending far beyond biophysical indicators and embracing ideas of soil, human, environmental, and ecosystem rights. As such, it has constantly been co-created in the never-ending process of human-nature interaction.

As such, we hope to raise awareness of the ethical dimension of soil management and encourage farmers, policymakers, researchers, foresters, businesses, and all actors involved in soil management to continue our work, to co-create, re-design, cooperate and explore new dimensions of social and environmental justice in their daily work to establish a new paradigm for the socially and environmentally just soil-management practices for soil-health oriented business models.

2 Introduction

This code of ethics was developed through a co-creative, participatory process under the NOVASOIL project. The code aims to create a shared vision grounded in the values and principles of soil health, forming the basis of a strategy for sustainable corporate land management governance for a wide range of stakeholders across the soil management sectors.

The ambition of the code is to develop a holistic approach and introduce a wide range of values that will serve as a basis for informed decisions.

The NOVASOIL project focuses on the societal and environmental benefits of investing in soil health by developing a toolbox for analysing, categorising, and promoting business models that generate economic value through sustainable soil management. Building on examples from across Europe and beyond, NOVASOIL co-develops soil-health-based business models with key stakeholders (public and private sectors: farmers, land managers, policymakers, researchers, etc.) and tests incentive mechanisms that reward practices that improve soil functions. Through an experimental and transdisciplinary approach that combines policy innovation, co-development, and a digital toolbox, the project seeks to make sustainable soil management profitable, socially inclusive, and aligned with international and European strategies, such as the Green Deal, Farm to Fork, and the EU Soil Strategy, including the Soil Monitoring Law (Novasoil project proposal).

2.1 Background

This code centres on the ethics of sustainable soil use. At the heart of its focus are ethical considerations linked to business models for soil health. Generally speaking, the ethical considerations of soil health management focus on balancing human land management needs (e.g., social and economic) with ecosystem integrity (e.g., biodiversity support, carbon sequestration) and long-term sustainability (e.g., implementing practices promoting soil health) while maintaining:

- 1) A reasonable price and the sound quality of products while ensuring the ethicalness of the product (e.g., by certification) for consumers, and;
- 2) Economic benefits for farmers and other actors in the food supply and the land management chain;
- 3) Provision of environmental public goods;
- 4) Ecosystem services linked to forestry sites and urban sites.

Sustainable soil management is now recognised as essential to supporting a projected 9.5 billion people by 2050 (Lal et al., 2014), indicating that unsustainable practices are not just environmentally destructive, but also fundamentally unethical.

Recognising soil as a living system (as the basis for ecological stability and human prosperity) calls for integrating the ethical dimension into land-use decision-making. Acknowledging and promoting responsible soil management is not only an environmental concern but also a moral commitment to sustaining life, preserving livelihoods, and ensuring fair distribution of the benefits and responsibilities of soil use (Hansjurgens et al., 2018). Ethical soil management and stewardship mean that the long-term viability of business models, with the potential of promoting stable food systems and rural economies, is inseparable from the health of the soil itself.

In this light, investing in soil health becomes both an economic opportunity and a moral obligation towards societal and planetary needs. (Thomson, 2017).

Soil health is critical, as it serves as a dynamic living system that needs to be preserved to provide essential ecosystem services and support food production, making it fundamental to productivity (Handayani et al., 2022). Specifically, healthy soils:

1. Sustain plant and animal production;
2. Control nutrient availability;
3. Support biodiversity;
4. Reduce erosion;
5. Enhance water and air quality;
6. Accumulate soil carbon.

Soil health is interlinked with plants, trees and crop health, with microorganism diversity playing a crucial role (Singh et al., 2024). Sustainable production depends on maintaining soil health, which requires holistic management strategies that preserve its multiple critical functions (Doran & Zeiss, 2000). Investing in soil health not only promotes crop productivity but also enhances the soil's resistance to climate impacts, strengthens biodiversity, retains water, and supports the livelihoods of rural communities (Hannam et al., 2025). While the soil-health-oriented investments may not show immediate returns, the long-term benefits demonstrate that sustainable soil management is a reasonable and strategic asset rather than a cost (Paustian et al., 2016).

The evidence shows that unsustainable soil management practices pose multiple ethical implications: first, they threaten the soil's "telos" or natural purposefulness, by which they violate the soil's right to maintain its physical, chemical, and biological cycles (van Mansvelt et al., 2021). The consequences, such as soil degradation in the form of erosion, nutrient depletion, and organic matter reduction, directly undermine the soil's capacity to support productivity and environmental quality (Karlen et al., 2015). This creates a chain of interrelated socio-ecological injustices and ethical dilemmas, ultimately harming both the natural and human worlds.

Soils require comprehensive protection because they are critical to a wide range of functions supporting the life of ecosystems and human biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, and food and crop production (Boer et al., 2014). According to Alblas et al. (2025), the gap in sufficient soil health protection stems from the fact that, while laws require a uniform approach, soils do not exist in a homogeneous form and, most importantly, are still not fully understood. In short, there is a need for additional legal instruments that provide comprehensive protection for soil health and support its irreplaceable role in human survival and environmental sustainability (Nwapi et al., 2015).

Since soil health is a critical condition for environmental and ecosystem stability and human prosperity, the loss of soil functions represents not only a biophysical degradation but also a failure to preserve an essential condition for the survival of present and future generations (Montanarella et. al., 2016).

Therefore, soil health promotion and protection pose a collective ethical responsibility to embrace ecological and environmental integrity and social justice as core pillars of sustainable land management.

2.2 Rationale for a code of ethics

Integrating the ethics dimension with soil management practices is essential for addressing human productive needs alongside the intrinsic ecological value of soil ecosystems (IPBES, 2018). The evidence suggests that in order to address these needs, a holistic approach that respects both production and natural soil systems is needed (van Mansvelt et al., 2021). To integrate ethics with these preconditions, it is important to treat soil as a non-renewable resource, valuing its preciousness while also acknowledging the responsible and participatory human dimensions of its management (De Corato et al., 2023).

The need for ethical guidelines is framed by the urgency of soil degradation in Europe, which could severely impact food security and rural livelihoods in the future. Several international and European frameworks already exist to guide ethical behaviour in agricultural and food production systems. However, they remain fragmented, as they do not provide comprehensive (and cross-cutting) ethical guidance that addresses both the socio-ecological and environmental dimensions of soil health. Some of the most prominent of these are as follows:

- 1) *EU Code of Conduct on Responsible Food Business and Marketing Practices* primarily addresses the ethical considerations related to food production, nutrition, consumer transparency, and responsible marketing within the agri-food supply chain;
- 2) *The UN Convention to Combat Desertification Code of Conduct* addresses land degradation and desertification risks through a policy and land-restoration optics.
- 3) The *International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC) Code of Conduct* focuses on phytosanitary standards and the prevention of pest spread in the trade.
- 4) *The FAO Voluntary Guidelines for Sustainable Soil Management (VGSSM)* provide a technical framework for soil conservation and ecosystem service protection, emphasising sustainability and stewardship.
- 5) *The FAO International Code of Conduct for the Sustainable Use and Management of Fertilisers* focuses on minimising pollution and promoting responsible input use.
- 6) National soil science society codes (e.g., in the UK, Australia, and the US) focus on promoting professional integrity and scientific responsibility.

- 7) The *EU Code of Conduct on Agricultural Data Sharing by Contractual Agreement* regulates the ethical use of data through principles of consent, privacy, and transparency, and recent *EU soil health strategies and environmental directives* embed values such as stewardship and intergenerational responsibility.

These (and other) documents we reviewed reveal some gaps concerning the integration of the ethics dimension with soil-related management. Firstly:

- 1) Most current codes address the later stages of food production and supply chains, and their ethical frameworks do not guide business practices or soil-related decisions across different sectors.
- 2) If they do, they primarily focus on the biophysical and environmental (and ecological) dimensions of soil health.
- 3) Fail to establish a comprehensive, unified, and coherent ethical framework for managing soil as a shared common good and addressing both the socio-ecological and environmental dimensions of soil management.

Another gap is that most existing codes are formulated as *codes of conduct*. These outline expected standards of behaviour, often within a specific legal context. This indicates a lack of guidance on the formulation of fundamental ethical principles and on the focus on general ethical responsibilities typical of the codes of ethics.¹

As a result, there is currently no overarching ethical framework for soil-health-oriented management that addresses both the ecological functions of soil and its socio-economic dimensions within business models, policy incentives, and land governance, and that is context-sensitive while also providing generalised guidance. This absence creates a conceptual and governance gap at a time when soils are threatened and commodified through various market initiatives (e.g., carbon markets)(Ullström; 2017).

2.3 Objectives

This code addresses the call for a focused, comprehensive, and overarching ethical framework that integrates both the environmental and socio-ecological dimensions of soil-health-related management.

Its objectives are to strengthen the legitimacy and transparency of investments in soil health and ensure that business models, policy incentives, and land governance mechanisms are guided by ecological responsibility, fairness, and inter- and intra-generational justice. The code aims to support sustainable and regenerative soil management practices, supporting the resilience and viability of rural economies and food chains, and securing the long-term capacity of soils to provide essential ecosystem services for the benefit of current and future generations.

¹ <https://www.ncoss.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Ethical-Frameworks.pdf>.

2.4 Nature and scope

This Code of Ethics is non-legally binding. It is grounded in principles aligned with the objectives of the NovaSoil project and relevant European strategies. The Code does not impose regulatory obligations; instead, it provides an ethical foundation for decision-making in soil health business models. It offers guiding values and principles that can inform strategic, context-specific decisions made by farmers, business actors, policymakers, and other soil management-related stakeholders. Its scope covers the entire soil-related value chain, aiming to promote sustainable, fair, and future-oriented soil stewardship.

2.5 Target audience

This code is intended for a broad range of stakeholders involved in soil-related decision-making and business practices. The primary target audience includes policymakers and bodies responsible for planning and implementation of soil management policies; farmers and farmer associations; forestry and other land management-related businesses, associations and institutions; researchers and academic institutions; and private and civil society actors.

3 Theoretical and conceptual foundations

For this document, we adopted an ethical approach that integrates considerations of the environmental (and ecological) and social dimensions of sustainable soil management. This approach was based on the combination of multidimensional environmental justice theory (Schlosberg, 2007) and the IPBES values framework with relation to sustainable land-use management.

The current scientific evidence suggests that to address the ethical dimension of sustainable soil management, three key mechanisms need to be addressed: 1) community involvement, where researchers collaborate directly with farmers (and a broader portfolio of stakeholders linked to soil management) to understand their lived experiences and incorporate their “funds of knowledge” (van Horne et al., 2022); 2) balancing intragenerational needs (current rural food security of marginalised communities) with intergenerational ecosystem sustainability (Sievers-Glotzbach et al., 2012); and 3) implementing procedural justice that recognises diverse stakeholder values and ensures equitable environmental management (Dawson et al., 2018). This suggests that the soil’s environmental and ecological quality is deeply interlinked with human equality and social justice issues, and that to achieve truly sustainable land management, it is vital to build on diverse knowledge systems and equitable decision-making processes (Agyeman et al., 2002).

Healthy soil, as a living system, provides many benefits to humans and natural ecosystems, thus possessing a range of values. The instrumental ones encompass, most notably, the ecosystem services (e.g., carbon sequestration, nutrient regulation) (Schmitt et al., 2022) or economic efficiency present when

sustainable land management improves crop production (Gamajunova et al., 2020). The relational values emerging from healthy soil refer to the human-nature relationship in the form of stewardship, care, responsibility or identity (Pape et al., 2023). These values significantly influence land management decisions (Arias-Arévalo et al., 2017), and promoting them could advance pro-social-ecological behaviour and sustainable land-use considerations across different contexts (Uehara et al., 2022). Finally, healthy soil possesses intrinsic values that extend far beyond its economic utility, underscoring its ecological and social importance. The intrinsic dimensions of soil include the following:

- 1) Soil is the most diverse habitat on the planet, playing a critical role in the ecosystems' functioning (Zhu et al., 2019);
- 2) Soil poses the cultural significance of human relationships and social functioning (Stronge et al., 2020);
- 3) Soil is a dynamic living system that sustains all the living processes (Handayani et al., 2022).

To acknowledge the soil's intrinsic value is to recognise its primary importance and, by extension, its rights (Phillips et al., 2020).

3.1 Operationalisation of the frameworks

To operationalise the ethical considerations within soil health business models, this code adopts an integrated ethical framework that considers both the environmental (and ecological) and socio-economic dimensions of sustainable soil management, where sustainability relies on balancing ecosystem integrity with human well-being. As Figure 2 illustrates, the guiding ethical principles were derived from the combination of the two frameworks and emerge along the two dimensions of soil management.

The environmental and ecological dimension is grounded in the recognition of soil's intrinsic value beyond its immediate economic utility (van Mansvelt et al., 2021). It emphasises prioritising ecosystem services and the long-term regenerative capacity of soil over short-term production gains (Lal et al., 2014).

The social and economic dimension is interlinked with principles of stewardship, participatory governance, and justice, with equitable distribution of costs and benefits, protection of vulnerable landscapes, and inter- and intra-generational fairness being central (Raies et al., 2023; Neyret et al., 2023; Kopittke et al., 2019).

Figure 1: Guiding ethical principles embedded in environmental and social dimensions of soil management; source: authors.

3.2 Definition of an ethical business model for soil health

In this document, the ethical business model for soil health is defined as:

- 1) A governance and economic framework incorporating practices focused on protection, restoration and enhancement of soil functions while also integrating shared ethical principles (e.g., stewardship, fairness, social responsibility).
- 2) A model that ensures that economic gains and benefits are achieved through regenerative and sustainable practices, while at the same time benefiting farmers, communities, and ecosystems.
- 3) A model integrating environmental sustainability with social responsibility by promoting inclusive decision-making, fair distribution of costs and benefits, transparency, and long-term ecological resilience.

At the heart of this conception of a business model is a recognition of soil as a living entity essential to safe food systems, climate change adaptation and mitigation, and biodiversity, thereby aligning business incentives with the ethical obligation to sustain soil health for present and future generations.

4 Process of developing the code

This code's creation comprised several phases. During the preparatory phase, we reviewed the existing literature on soil ethics, sustainable land management, soil health, business models and land management policies. We searched for articles listed in the WOS and SCOPUS databases using the following keywords:

- 1) Ethics and sustainable land management;
- 2) Soil ethics;
- 3) Ethics and soil health;
- 4) Ethics and business models in land and soil management;
- 5) Environmental justice, sustainable land use, soil health;
- 6) IPBES values framework sustainable land use, soil health, and social justice;
- 7) Intrinsic, relational and instrumental values and sustainable land use;

8) Ethics and land management policies, laws, regulations and policies.

Firstly, we focused on review papers to identify those that play a key role in our research. Secondly, we sorted the papers based on their relevance to the research topic and the frequency with which they were cited. This step helped us to determine the framework for exploring the existing ethical dimensions of soil management.

The second step was to review the existing codes of ethics and conduct aligned with prominent European and international policies. This step was crucial for mapping the current policy landscape, with an emphasis on the ethical frameworks it includes. This step was also important for determining the practical implications for soil-health business models by focusing on the values these documents included. Subsequently, we finalised this process by reviewing the existing empirical data (e.g., stakeholder interviews and participatory workshops).

Finally, we clustered the identified values based on their relationships to determine patterns that serve as a basis for defining the key pillars of an ethical business model for soil health.

Figure 2 shows the process of code creation:

CODE OF ETHICS FOR SOIL-HEALTH BUSINESS MODEL

Figure 2: The process of the code of ethics creation; source: authors.

The following subchapters describe the data creation process in detail.

4.1 Data sets and data creation process

The first phase of data creation comprised:

- 1) A systematic examination of prominent European and international policies concerning the agricultural sector (with a special emphasis on those relating to soil management), with a specific focus on identifying existing codes of conduct or ethics. These were subsequently categorised and enrolled into the analytical framework:

EU

- Forestry Strategy: under general EC
(https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/08709964-ef08-4332-a899-a456bdf0bff5_en?filename=f2f_sfpd_coc_final_en.pdf)
- SDGs: <https://sustainabledevelopmentcouncil.org/code-of-ethics/>
- Green Deal: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/qanda_21_3386/QANDA_21_3386_EN.pdf
- Farm to Fork Strategy: https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy/sustainable-food-processing/code-conduct_en
- Biodiversity Strategy: under general EC (see above)
- new Soil Strategy: under general EC (see above)
- Zero Pollution Strategy: under the general EC (see above)
- Long-term Vision for Rural Areas: under general EC (see above)
- Soil monitoring law
- Carbon farming regulations
- FEFAC

GLOBAL

- UNCCD: https://www.unccd.int/sites/default/files/2022-07/SPI%20Code%20of%20Conduct_110117.pdf
- UN CBD: <https://www.cbd.int/traditional/code/ethicalconduct-brochure-en.pdf>
- UN FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation)
- OECD
- IPCC ´s conventions (Rotterdam, plant protection, pesticide control, rice convention)

Figure 3 presents the relational mapping of these policy instruments and their ethical dimensions.

Figure 3: The links between the prominent EU and international soil management policies; source: authors.

The empirical data set comprised data collected through interviews and participatory workshops, involving over two hundred stakeholders across a couple of dozen workshops, focus groups, multiplayer events and individual interviews. The participating stakeholder groups included farmers, representatives of farmer associations, policymakers, researchers, and actors from the agricultural, forestry and business sectors.

4.2 Analysis process

Both data sets (codes of ethics and conduct and empirical data created during interviews, stakeholder workshops, focus groups and multiplayer events) were analysed using qualitative thematic analysis. The analysis was based on inductive open coding in MAXQDA 2024. We analysed codes using two interpretative text analysis methods: literal reading, which focused exclusively on values explicitly stated in the text, and thematic reading, which identified implicit value structures and patterns across the documents. Through this process, core values were identified.

The empirical data (interview transcripts and workshop, multiplayer events and focus group notes) were also inductively coded to identify values and ethical considerations related to soil and land use expressed by stakeholders.

This analytical process enabled an assessment of the normative values present in existing ethical frameworks and of empirically derived stakeholder views on ethics. After analysing these two datasets individually and interpreting the results, we compared the outcomes and identified crossovers and differences.

The shared and context-specific values emerging from both datasets provided the empirical and conceptual foundation for the ethical guidelines developed in this code.

4.3 Case studies overview²

The empirical part of the research was grounded in the case studies, which provided a rich platform (and context) for all the stakeholder interactions. The following paragraphs provide a brief overview of all of them.

Integrated production in the vineyards (NBU)

The case study's overarching aim is twofold: first, to improve soil conditions in commercial vineyards by reducing erosion, enhancing soil organic matter, and stabilising yields; and second, to translate these biophysical improvements into tangible economic value through product differentiation, certification of traditional products, and alliances with wine tourism.

Integrated production in Estonia (METK)

Estonia's integrated production case revolves around METK, a state R&D institute under the Ministry of Rural Affairs. METK breeds crops, produces certified seed across ~1,100 ha, and, among others, runs applied research on how catch crops, tillage systems and fertilisation affect the physical, chemical and biological properties of soils.

CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture: Payment for Ecosystem Services (UNIPI)

The case study's ambition is to translate this scientific evidence base into a practical Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) architecture that rewards farmers for verified improvements in soil condition while maintaining commercially viable farming operations. Rather than asking farmers to adopt soil-friendly practices based on goodwill alone, the model creates clear financial incentives tied to measurable environmental outcomes, backed by credible long-term data that reduce risk for both farmers and paying agencies.

District of the Sands: Carbon Credits (DELTA & UNIFE)

Strategically, it seeks to turn that stewardship into cash flow through a Sustainability District, an integrated model that blends carbon farming with certification/production standards and value-chain signalling for coastal horticulture. The District is conceived not as a single project, but as a portfolio: multiple farms, coordinated practices, shared monitoring and an institutional backbone that lowers costs and raises credibility.

Rueda, Organic vineyards: Integrated production

Economically, holdings stack a predictable public base with small but reliable top-ups, while saving on inputs through composted by-products and shared kits. Institutionally, the case shows how IP certification + eco-schemes + light, result-based MRV can be woven into a coherent, low-friction offer that is credible to buyers, workable for administrators and usable for growers.

² This subchapter was derived from the text of delivery 1.4.

Integrated Production in Andalusian Olive Groves (ASAJA)

Integrated Production (IP) in Andalusian olive groves is one of the best examples of a reliable, profitable business model that simultaneously promotes soil health. Since its implementation in 2005, this system has expanded significantly in area, covering both table olive and olive oil groves. Its central objective is to combine productivity with sustainability, offering a product with added environmental and social value through the official Integrated Production label.

Bodenfruchtbarkeitsfonds: Payments for Ecosystem services (TUM)

Overall, farmers perceived the Soil Fertility Fund as a practical, trust-based, and empowering initiative. It gives them both the freedom and the professional support needed to implement soil-building practices effectively. Compared to public programmes, the fund was viewed as more holistic, less bureaucratic, and more focused on the soil itself rather than on narrow carbon metrics. This combination of ecological conviction, practical support, and social learning explains the high level of satisfaction and engagement among participating farms.

Payments for Ecosystem Services in the Tamarguillo Park

The Tamarguillo Park is an ample urban green space where soils have been exposed to contamination and constant pressure from housing, traffic and planning decisions. Framed within NOVASOIL as a Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) pilot, the case addresses two connected challenges: the biophysical degradation of urban soils (contamination, low SOM, compaction and sealing) and the institutional gap between the park's management budgets and the public benefits those soils provide (run-off control, cooling, biodiversity, recreation and property-value uplift).

CS: ZSA DIH System (ZSA)

The Latvian case study builds on the integration of soil data and soil management practices into a digital mapping service hosted within the ZSA Digital Innovation Hub (DIH). It aims to address gaps in information exchange among state and local authorities, landowners, and the general public on soil health and management practices, with the sole aim of increasing the adoption of soil-friendly practices that would improve soil health, especially organic matter.

A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas: Value chain (UNIFI)

This case study originated from an integrated supply chain project funded under the European Union's rural development policy, which brought together a collaborative network of research centres, private companies, farmers, and public administrations. The project's fundamental insight recognises that marginal areas cannot compete with more productive lowland regions through conventional commodity cereal production alone.

Instead, the strategic approach involves transforming existing agricultural systems by introducing perennial medicinal and aromatic plants (particularly lavender) while simultaneously transitioning from conventional to organic farming.

5 Results

5.1 Values from the existing codes

Across the analysed codes of conduct and ethics, we identified the following groups of values:

1. Human rights-related values (e.g., respect for human dignity, equality);
2. Virtues-related values (e.g., respect, humility);
3. Social and relational values (e.g., inclusion, transparency);
4. Environmental values (e.g., stewardship);
5. Performance-related values (e.g., excellence).

The following table shows all of the identified values clustered under the abovementioned categories:

Table 1: Values categories with their definition and values identified in the existing codes; source: authors.

Value category	Values	Definition
1. Human rights-related values	Respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, rule of law, respect for human rights (including rights of minorities)	Values addressing fundamental freedoms and the inherent worth of a human being. They refer to decisions and practices that embrace justice, participation, and non-discrimination in accordance with universal human rights principles.
2. Virtue-related values	Open-mindedness, tolerance, integrity, respect, responsibility, humility, humanity	Values that guide ethical behaviour. They reflect virtues such as honesty, empathy, accountability, and the ability to act with moral excellence toward others and nature.
3. Social and relational values	Inclusion, fairness, transparency, and information confidentiality	Values related to relationships between individuals, communities and institutions. They are linked with trust, equity, accountability, and mutual respect in collaborative governance and decision-making.

Value category	Values	Definition
4. Environmental values	Stewardship	Values linked with the intrinsic worth of nature and the human duty to care for, protect, and regenerate natural systems.
5. Performance-related values	Professional knowledge, Excellence	Values linked with competence. They refer to evidence-based practice, innovation, quality outcomes, and a commitment to high standards in managing soil and agricultural systems.

5.1.1 Observed patterns

Across the codes, we observed several patterns. Firstly, the identified categories of values (human-rights related, environmental, etc.) cover both dimensions of sustainable soil management (environmental and social), indicating a trend towards a holistic approach to the soil-health-related practices. However, these values appear across various documents (and are not unified under a single framework), indicating that a unified, cross-cutting ethical framework guiding sustainable soil management (and, subsequently, ethical business models) is currently missing.

Secondly, the observed patterns that can be generalised (and thus serve as a basis for a more unified framework suggest the following:

- 1) Access to soil and its benefits must be *equitable and inclusive*. This reflects emphasis on the distributive dimension of justice, emphasising the fair distribution of the costs and benefits of sustainable soil management, as well as inclusion of all the relevant stakeholders (both on the individual and community level) into all the stages of land management governance.
- 2) Sustainable soil management should be centred around *collaboration and shared stewardship*. This suggests a proposal for participatory decision-making that invites all relevant stakeholders to co-create and sustain solutions.
- 3) *Knowledge-sharing* should be an ethical imperative to achieve fair governance. This stresses the need for transparent communication and capacity-building.
- 4) *Transparency and social accountability* reflect the emphasis on reliable and verifiable practices, transparent reporting, and mechanisms that ensure trust between various groups of stakeholders.

5.2 Values derived from the empirical data

The key value categories identified based on the empirical data were the following:

- Accountability and transparency-related values (e.g., integrity);

- Collective responsibility-related values (e.g., cooperation along the supply chain);
- Working conditions-related values (e.g., recognition of the farmers' work importance).

Table 2 demonstrates all of the identified values clustered under the abovementioned categories:

Table 2: Values categories with their definition and values based on the empirical data; source: authors.

Value category	Values	Definition
1. Accountability and transparency-related values	Transparency, accountability, responsibility, scientific credibility, trust, proportional income, long-term commitment, and precaution against greenwashing.	These values refer to the need for verifiable evidence, transparent communication, and consistency between claims and actions.
2. Collective responsibility-related values	Community cooperation, knowledge sharing, inclusion, social responsibility, territorial governance, environmental stewardship, cohesion, shared value-chain commitment, resilience.	These values refer to the cooperation and coordinated action among farmers, policymakers, businesses, and consumers.
3. Working conditions-related values	Fair treatment, recognition of farmers' work value, equity in working standards, a safe working environment, and individual well-being.	These values refer to the human dimension of sustainable soil management.

5.2.1 Observed patterns

One of the first notable patterns among the values and categories identified from the empirical data was a strong orientation towards working conditions and the work process. While the values present in the existing codes covered a wider portfolio of themes, the Straightforward orientation towards more "daily-reality „oriented values was evident in the empirical data.

Secondly, unlike the values identified in the existing codes, the empirically based values reflected the socio-economic dimension of sustainable soil management much more than the environmental one. This, once again, underscores the need to integrate ethical considerations with the lived realities of the relevant stakeholders.

6. Implications: the ethical business model for soil health

The ethical frameworks within European and international agricultural policies indicate an orientation towards a more universal business model for soil health, grounded evenly in both dimensions of sustainable land management: the environmental and the social.

However, empirical data indicate that a viable business model for soil health that reflects stakeholders' needs (and thus has the potential to be implemented and sustained) spans across multiple dimensions and stages of sustainable soil management.

Based on the empirical data, the ethical business models for soil health need to:

- 1) *Be credible and science-based*, preventing misleading practices (e.g., greenwashing) and supporting public confidence and legitimacy regarding soil-related incentives and investments. *Accountability and transparency* in such a model serve as safeguards against exploitation (as, for example, in the case of a carbon credit business model and result-based business incentives that could measure effective soil health improvement) and ensure that economic benefits are distributed based on measurable contributions to soil improvement, including the focus on individual farm performance.
- 2) *Promote interdependence and collaborative responsibility* for maintaining soil functions for the common good. This means active support for *participatory governance, shared learning, and collective investment* in soil regeneration and sustainable practices, rather than practices promoting competitiveness or individualistic approaches. In this case, the creation of an institution that would help the farmers with the monitoring and support them in transition towards soil regeneration (also providing the technical and informational support and funding) would be vital.
- 3) Focus on the social dimension of sustainable soil management by promoting *dignity, safe working conditions, and fairness* for the people who manage the soil and depend on it. This also relates to the call to acknowledge the value of farmers' work by recognising their contributions to society and ensuring their fair compensation and safety.

Based on the identified patterns, an ethical business model for soil health should serve as a **governance framework** grounded in **fairness, shared responsibility, and stewardship**. This means it should ensure **inclusive access to land-based benefits**, protect and include marginalised stakeholder groups, and enable **participation in decision-making processes**.

Business operations under such a framework **need to promote collaboration** rather than competition **along the whole supply chain**. **Knowledge exchange** and **fair benefit-sharing** should be institutionalised **to prevent power asymmetries and ensure that risks and rewards are fairly distributed**.

Furthermore, **soil must be treated as a living system**, requiring **long-term investment** that **safeguards ecosystem functions** and food security **for present and future generations**.

Transparency and social accountability should be **mandatory** aspects of soil-related business models, including **regular reporting and participatory monitoring**, to ensure the **legitimacy and ethical integrity** of soil health investments.

An ethical business model for soil health **should ensure environmental integrity** and shared responsibility among all stakeholders. Such a model **should actively prevent the abuse of incentives** by **requiring compliance and accountability from both public and private actors**.

Finally, ethical soil-health business practices must also **encourage consumer responsibility**, acknowledging that **market demand plays a critical role in shaping land management outcomes**. With this in mind, the model should **prioritise the moral obligation to support vulnerable landscapes and the farmers** who manage them, ensuring that **their work is valued and recognised** and their **working conditions are fair and safe**. This means a **stewardship-based approach** promoting **interdependence and long-term sustainability**.

7. Conclusions: case studies-specific ethical considerations for business models for soil health

The case studies demonstrated that, from the perspective of local stakeholders, a successful sustainable soil-health business model relies heavily on *active stakeholder participation, well-targeted incentives, and context-specific support*. Identifying and using more effective stimuli to encourage farmer participation in research was essential, particularly for testing carbon farming and privately funded soil biodiversity promotion and protection schemes.

Participatory workshops were recognised as a vital tool for communication and cooperation, in which actors had the chance to co-develop solutions, in line with *principles of inclusion, transparency, and shared stewardship as ethical cornerstones*. Stakeholders highlighted the importance of *empathy from project partners* and the need to ensure that proposed business models are *accessible* for all the “users”.

The promotion of traditional crop varieties, cultural identity, and territorial values was recognised as a strong motivator for stakeholder engagement.

For example, actors expressed willingness to adopt agroecological practices when these practices aligned with local values and provided clear benefits for the local communities. This reflects relational values and intergenerational responsibility, indicating the need to conceive the land not just as a “production asset,” but also as cultural and ecological heritage.

The ethical concerns included high certification costs, low consumer awareness, and unequal access to policy support for small or unregistered producers, as identified systemic injustices. Additionally, some universal EU-level practices were not perceived as suitable for local climates, underscoring the importance of context sensitivity.

6 Final ethical considerations

We dedicate this section to the final ethical considerations that arose throughout the code-creation process:

- 1) For the ethical soil management and governance to be truly socially just, it must be grounded within the existing property rights systems, therefore promoting the balance between the legitimate public interests and the autonomy of landowners to address both the collective and individual rights.
- 2) At the same time, it is crucial to protect the interests of farmers (and any other relevant stakeholder groups on the individual and collective levels), as they should have equal access to transparent information, technical support and the ability to formulate (and participate in the process of taking and implementing) the informed decisions.
- 3) The ethical dimension of soil management also encompasses the power position of researchers, policymakers, and other experts in shaping soil-related decisions within the decision-making processes to prevent the generation of power asymmetries and the exclusion of some actors from any relevant processes.
- 4) Embedding ethics into research practice must promote a culture of responsibility, humility, and (self)reflexivity, and the protection of the enrolled stakeholders, as they provide much of their data, must be ensured..

7 References

Agyeman, J., Bullard, R. D., & Evans, B. (2002). Exploring the nexus: Bringing together sustainability, environmental justice and equity. *Space & Polity*, 6(1), 77–90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562570220137907>.

Alori, E. T., & Nwapi, C. (2015). *The international legal regime for sustainable soil*. In R. Ako & D. Olawuyi (Eds.), *Food and agricultural law: Readings on sustainable agriculture and the law in Nigeria* (pp. 98–114). Afe Babalola University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2641138>.

Alblas et al. (2025). Bridging Law and Soil Science to Promote Soil Health. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 76(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.70127>.

Arias-Arévalo, P., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Martín-López, B., & Pérez-Rincón, M. (2018). Widening the evaluative space for ecosystem services: A taxonomy of plural values and valuation methods. *Environmental Values*, 27(1), 29–53. <https://doi.org/10.3197/096327118X15144698637513>.

De Corato, U. (2024). Impact of the sustainable agricultural practices for governing soil health from the perspective of a rising agri-based circular bioeconomy. *Applied Soil Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.10519>.

Dawson, A. & Knowles, O. (2018). To grid or not to grid – a review of soil sampling strategies. In: Farm environmental planning – Science, policy and practice. (Eds L. D. Currie and C. L. Christensen).

Doran, J. W., & Zeiss, M. R. (2000). Soil health and sustainability: Managing the biotic component of soil quality. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 15(1), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2023.105199>.

Gamajunova, V. V., Kuvshinova, A. O., Kudrina, V. S., & Sydiakina, O. V. (2020). Influence of biologics on water consumption of winter barley and sunflower in conditions of the Ukrainian Southern Steppe. *Innovative Solutions in Modern Science*, (6 (42)), 149–176. [10.26886/2414-634X.6\(42\)2020.9](https://doi.org/10.26886/2414-634X.6(42)2020.9).

Handayani, I. P., & Hale, C. (2022). Healthy soils for productivity and sustainable development in agriculture. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1018(1), 012038. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1018/1/012038>.

Hannam, J. A., Harris, M., Deeks, L., Hoskins, H., Hutchison, J., Withers, A. J., Harris, J. A., Way, L., & Rickson, R. J. (2025). Developing a multifunctional indicator framework for soil health. *Ecological Indicators*, 175, 113515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113515>

Hansjürgens, B., Lienkamp, A., & Möckel, S. (2018). Justifying soil protection and sustainable soil management: Creation-ethical, legal and economic considerations. *Sustainability*, 10(10), 3807. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10103807>.

Ines, R. (2023). Clay-induced permeability decline in sandstone reservoirs. *Applied Clay Science*, 240, 106905. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-6505\(23\)00138-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-6505(23)00138-4).

IPBES (2018): Summary for policymakers of the assessment report on land degradation and restoration of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. R. Scholes, L. Montanarella, A. Brainich, N. Barger, B. ten Brink, M. Cantele, B. Erasmus, J. Fisher, T. Gardner, T. G. Holland, F. Kohler, J. S. Kotiaho, G. Von Maltitz, G. Nangendo, R. Pandit, J. Parrotta, M. D. Potts, S. Prince, M. Sankaran and L. Willemen (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 44 pages.

Karlen, D. L., & Rice, C. W. (2015). Soil degradation: Will humankind ever learn? *Sustainability*, 7(9), 12490–12501. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su70912490>.

Kopittke, P. M., Menzies, N. W., Wang, P., McKenna, B. A., Lombi, E., McLaughlin, M. J., ... Mueller, U. (2019). Soil and the intensification of agriculture for global food security. *Environment International*, 132, 105078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.105078>.

Lal, R. (2014). Principles and practices of soil resource conservation. In eLS. John Wiley & Sons Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470015902.A0003295.PUB2>.

Montanarella, L., Pennock, D. J., McKenzie, N., Badraoui, M., Chude, V., Baptista, I., Mamo, T., Yemefack, M., Singh Aulakh, M., Yagi, K., Hong, S. Y., Vijarnsorn, P., Zhang, G.-L., Arrouays, D., Black, H., Krasilnikov, P., Sobocká, J., Alegre, J., Henríquez, C. R., de Lourdes Mendonça-Santos, M., ... Alavi-Panah, S. K. (2016). The world's soils are under threat. *SOIL*, 2, 79–82. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-2-79-2016>.

Neyret, M., Peter, S., Le Provost, G., Boch, S., Boesing, A. L., Bullock, J. M., Hölzel, N., Klaus, V. H., Kleinebecker, T., Krauss, J., Müller, J., Müller, S., Ammer, C., Buscot, F., Ehbrecht, M., Fischer, M., Goldmann, K., Jung, K., Mehring, M., Müller, T., Renner, S. C., Schall, P., Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Westphal, C., Wubet, T., & Manning, P. (2023). Landscape management strategies for multifunctionality and social equity. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(4), 391–403. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-01045-w>.

NovaSoil project proposal.

Paustian, K., Lehmann, J., Ogle, S., Reay, D., Robertson, G. P., & Smith, P. (2016). Climate-smart soils. *Nature*, 532(7597), 49–57. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature17174>.

Phillips, H. R. P., Beaumelle, L., Eisenhauer, N., Hines, J., & Smith, L. C. (2020). Lessons from the WBF2020: Extrinsic and intrinsic value of soil organisms. *Soil Organisms*, 92(2), 121–127. <https://doi.org/10.25674/so92iss2pp121>.

Schmitt, T. M., Riebl, R., Martín-López, B., Hänsel, M., & Koellner, T. (2022). Plural valuation in space: Mapping values of grasslands and their ecosystem services. *Ecosystems and People*, 18(1), 258–274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2022.2065361>.

Sievers-Glotzbach, S. (2014). Reconciling intragenerational and intergenerational environmental justice in Philippine agriculture: The MASIPAG farmer network. *Ethics, Policy & Environment*, 17(1), 52–68. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21550085.2014.885170>.

Singh, A. K., Pandey, A. K., & Kumari, N. (2024). Unravelling the dynamics of soil health: Key insight and future direction. *Asian Journal of Science and Plant Nutrition*, 10(3), 433–443. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajssp/2024/v10i3355>.

Schlosberg, D. (2007). *Defining environmental justice: Theories, movements, and nature*. Oxford University Press.

Stronge, D. C., Kannemeyer, R. L., Harmsworth, G. R., & Stevenson, B. A. (2023). Achieving soil health in Aotearoa New Zealand through a pluralistic values-based framework: *Mauri ora ki te whenua, mauri ora ki te tangata*. *Sustainability Science*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01269-x>.

Thompson, P. B. (2017). *The spirit of the soil: Agriculture and environmental ethics* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

Uehara, T., Sakurai, R., & Hidaka, T. (2022). The importance of relational values in gaining people's support and promoting their involvement in social-ecological system management: A comparative analysis. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 1001180. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1001180>.

van Mansvelt, J. D., Struik, P. C., Bos, A., Daub, W., Sprangers, D., van den Berg, M., Vingerhoets, M., & Zoeteman, K. (2021). Changing ground: Handling tensions between production ethics and environmental ethics of agricultural soils. *Sustainability*, 13(23), 13291. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132313291>.

Ullström (2017). The political ecology of carbon: Commodification, colonialism and debt in carbon offsetting under the Clean Development Mechanism. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/8897565>.

Van Horne, Y. O., Alcalá, C. S., Peltier, R. E., Quintana, P. J. E., Seto, E., Gonzales, M., Johnston, J. E., Montoya, L. D., Quirós-Alcalá, L., & Beamer, P. I. (2023). An applied environmental justice framework for exposure science. *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology*, 33(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-022-00422-z>.

Zhu, M., Feng, Q., Qin, Y., Cao, J., Zhang, M., Liu, W., Deo, R. C., Zhang, C., Li, R., & Li, B. (2019). The role of topography in shaping the spatial patterns of soil organic carbon. *Catena*, 176, 296-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2019.01.029>.

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